

Psoriasis and it's Homoeopathic Management

Dr. Rachna Kalra

PG. Scholar, Department of Homeopathic Materia Medica
Sri Guru Nanak Dev Homoeopathic Medical College and Hospital
Ludhiana, Punjab.

Abstract:- Psoriasis is a common chronic papulosquamous skin disease occurring worldwide, presenting at any age and leading to a substantial burden for individuals and society. characterized. It is characterized by accelerated tumor necrosis factor- α /interleukin-23/interleukin-17 axis, hyperproliferation and abnormal differentiation of epidermal keratinocytes. Homoeopathy plays a vital role in treating skin diseases According to Dr. Hahnemann The origin of the disease is of Psoric Origin when it is not treated properly suppression of the disease takes place. Disease Originated at a dyanamic level and Homoeopathic medicines also acted on deeper and dynamic level.

Keywords:- Psoriasis, Inflammation, Homoeopathy

I. PSORIASIS

Psoriasis is a chronic dermatosis characterized by an unpredictable course of remissions and relapses and presence

➤ *Pathophysiology:*

Fig 1:- Pathophysiology

at typical sites of well-defined erythematous papules and plaques, which are surmounted with large, silvery loose scales.

A. *Etiology:*

Unknown, but many factors have been noticed:-

- Genetic -may be autosomal dominant
- Physical trauma like scratches, surgical incisions and injuries
- Infections like beta- hemolytic streptococcal infection precipitates Guttae Psoriasis, HIV infection precipitates explosive psoriasis
- Drugs like antimalarials, NSAIDS, Corticosteroids

➤ *Epidemiology:*

1% population is affected and it occurs at any age. Both sexes are equally affected and most patients are worse in winters

B. Clinical Features:

- A patchy rash that varies widely in how it looks from person to person, ranging from spots of dandruff-like scaling to major eruptions over much of the body
- Rashes that vary in color, tending to be shades of purple with gray scale on brown or Black skin and pink or red with silver scale on white skin
- Small scaling spots (commonly seen in children)
- Dry, cracked skin that may bleed
- Itching, burning or soreness
- Cyclic rashes that flare for a few weeks or months and then subside

C. Classification of Psoriasis :

Classification is of various type

➤ *On the basis of morphology :*

- **Psoriasis Vulgaris**- commonest form of psoriasis .Primary lesion is a mildly itchy plaque or papule which is well demarcated lesion where scaling may be absent, indurated, silvery scaly , discoid in nature and may vary in size and number

➤ *On the basis of variants:*

- **Guttate Psoriasis**-occurs In children and adolescents by streptococcal tonsillitis lesions appear in several crops . Mainly trunk is involved.
- **Rupoid Psoriasis**-Heaped up scales so the lesion appears conical adherent to underlying skin such lesions are present in Reiter's Syndrome.

➤ *On the basis of site:*

- **Flexural Psoriasis**-mainly in elderly females than males. Lesions present in moist friction prone area like groins, axilla , inframammary folds well defined salmon pink lesion
- **Scalp Psoriasis**-Indurated asbestos like scaly plaques present in occiput may spill into forehead and nape of neck
- **Penile Psoriasis**- occur in uncircumcised male scaling is absent in glans but lesions continue to be erythematous and well defined . In circumcised male lesions on glans like psoriatic lesions elsewhere
- **Psoriasis of palms and soles**-Bilateral involvement well defined silvery thickened plaques adherent to palms and soles unlike loose scales on other parts
- Psoriasis of Joints and Nails are also seen in today's life

D. Complications:

- Erythrodermic Psoriasis
- Pustular Psoriasis
- Psoriatic Arthritis

E. Investigations:

- Biopsy
- Biochemical Changes
- Radiological Changes

F. Diagnosis –

It is based on morphology of lesion, aggravating factors, distribution of lesion and its associated symptoms

➤ *Differential Diagnosis:*

- Discoid eczema
- Seborrheic dermatitis
- Pityriasis Rosea
- Candida intertrigo

G. Treatment:

It is based on totality of symptoms on the basis of symptom similarity according to Homeopathic Principles given by Dr. Hahnemann in Organon Of Medicine But few remedies of psoriasis are as follows :

➤ *Calcarea Sulph*

- It is indicated in cases of psoriasis eruptions are chiefly located on the scalp , extremities and back
- Scarlet red in appearance with lichenification of the surrounding skin.
- Severe burning and itching which is worse in warm room from warm bathing better by cold application and cold bath.
- Due to presence of secondary infection psoriatic eruptions suppurate which heal with the formation of thick yellow scabs.
- Discharges are greenish yellow , acrid and offensive

➤ *Clematis Erecta*

- Affected mostly on those individuals who are exposed to gonorrhoea or syphilis or individuals who consumed compound of mercury either locally or internally
- Unique feature of this remedy is profuse desquamation with severe itching worse washing in cold water
- Eruptions are present on face, hands and scalp especially around occiput
- Eruptions has characteristic modality that it gets worse during ascending moon and as the moon descends eruptions are better

➤ *Psorinum*

- Eruptions occur only in winter. Skin is dry, rough, scabby and greasy
- Nape of neck, scalp, folds of the skin and groin region affected
- Itching intolerable which are worse by heat of bed
- Patient scratches till it becomes raw and bleeds
- It is usually indicated when well related remedies fail to relieve or permanently cure or when sulphur seems indicated but fails to relieve
- Patient is extremely chilly and hungry with foul carrion like odour

II. CONCLUSION

It concludes that homoeopathy treats the psoriasis as well as other skin diseases very affectively. Homoeopathy Treats the Man in Disease Not Disease in Man. Medicine is prescribed on the basis of symptoms similarity according to the guidelines of Homeopathic principles given by Dr Hahnemann in Organon of Medicine & Chronic Diseases.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Miller, Jeffrey H.; Marks, James G. (2006). Lookingbill and Marks' Principles of Dermatology, Saunders
- [2]. Treatment of skin diseases A Practical Guide by Zohra Zaidi & Khalid Hussain
- [3]. Illustrated Synopsis of Dermatology & Sexual Transmitted Diseases By Neena Khanna
- [4]. The Lancet › lancet › article › PIIS0140-6736(20)32549-6 › fulltext
- [5]. www.mdpi.com › ...
- [6]. Homeopathic literature from Diseases of the skin including the EXANTHEMATA by FAROKH J. MASTER 2005 edition B.JAIN PUBLISHERS PVT. LTD
- [7]. Samuel lilanthal, Homoeopathic Therapeutics, The classical therapeutic hints B.Jain Publishers 1985
- [8]. William boericke, Boreicke's NewManual of Homoeopathic Materia Medica with Repertory ,B.Jain large print publisher.